

FDO Bulletin 2023-1 April 2023

Participate in Working Meetings and Taskforces

(see below)

Mark the date of the 2nd FDO Conference (20-22.3.24)

(see below)

FDO Work after the Leiden Conference

The Leiden conference was a milestone for the work on FAIR Digital Objects, since the FDO Forum managed to do the basic specification work and bring together a sizable and engaged community all based on voluntary work. The FDO Forum started its work in January 2022 with many questions what FDOs are and only two years later the Working Groups managed to present clear specifications. There is still much to do and essential gaps need to be tackled, but the conference showed that the FDO Forum indeed can switch its modus of work. It was seen as a relatively closed group which was the result of the will to make fast progress. It will now turn towards more open workshops and working meetings and thus lowering the thresholds for interested people to become engaged. And it will focus on implementations including a larger integrated testbed. As a consequence of the Leiden conference, we also did much restructuring work to adapt to the new modus.

The current versions of the specification and roadmap documents are here: <https://fairdo.org/specifications/>

2nd FDO Conference 21-22. March 2024 in Berlin

From 20 to 22. March 2024 the second FDO Conference will be held in Berlin under the slogan:

FAIR Digital Objects: From Theory to Practice

Implementing professional solutions across sectors

Aligned with the conference will be a hackathon (18.3) and a training day (19.3.). Reserve the conference and hands-on days in your agenda, inform your colleagues about this event and motivate them to participate. There will be no fees for the participation at the conference. For the training days some fees will be requested. The conference steering and program committees have started their work. All relevant information will be disseminated via this website which will be created soon: <https://fairdo.org/fdo2024-conference-2/> If your institution or initiatives wants to appear as supporter of the coming FDO conference, please, send us a note.

Strategy Discussion

Two organisational results became obvious during the Leiden Conference: (1) We will have to establish an organisational form until the second conference in March 2024. A strategy group is currently discussing and evaluating different options. Results will be communicated. (2) We want to achieve a more open interaction to include more experts in our work. Workshops, Working Meetings and Taskforce meetings should be organised in an open fashion and we will improve stepwise.

FDO Forum Groups & Committees

Due to the achieved milestone at the conference, we realised a change in the working groups and committees of the FDOF. Some colleagues stopped their contributions to the Steering Committee and also some working groups redefined their tasks and membership. We would like to thank all those colleagues who stopped now for their great contributions in the first 2 years. The **Steering Group** still takes all final decisions of FDOF. In addition, the **Executive Committee** with seven members will act on a more operational level. Coordination of all work will still be done by the four **co-chairs**: Christine Kirkpatrick, Dimitris Koureas, George Strawn and Peter Wittenburg.

With the **Technical Advisory Committee (TAC)**, a new board as been established that will give advice on all kinds of technical matters relevant for FDOs to the SC and EC. In an open process, colleagues with deep knowledge about FDOs could volunteer for membership and where finally appointed by SC. The two Working Groups, **Technical Specification and Implementation Group (TSIG)** and **Basic Infrastructure Group (BIG)**, decided to merge, since it turned out that after the end of the start-up phase the topics of the two groups had an increasing overlap. They will continue the work under the label TSIG.

Due to the open workshops FDOF realises that **new WGs** and **Task Forces** will be started some of them jointly with RDA to tackle specific aspects that emerge from the discussions. It is the intention to have open interactions to make progress.

The **FDO Community** covers currently about 500 experts from many different countries. Still a registration via the website is sufficient to be part of the information flow. It should be noted that the FDOF realises that the geographical balance has not yet been improved substantially. This is probably due to the specific program of the FDO Forum which is not yet understood broadly. New attempts will be made until the conference 2024.

Participation: *It should also be noted that experts interested in and/or active with FDOs are of course welcome to participate in the FDO Working Groups or kick-off a new one. A simple email to the FDO secretariat explaining the interest would be sufficient.*

Lecture and Workshop Program

As one of the major consequences after the Leiden conference, the FDOF decided to intensify its open lecture and open workshop program with the intention to have both events every month (except July and August). The program for the first half year can be seen here: <https://fairdo.org/events/>. Access to all materials of all events is open and can be started here:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1e1MkSsOw4ni1NurKsl9xUO7ZmGdpVZLu?usp=sharing>

The FDOF is currently discussing the events for the second half of the year and we are requested to open up this discussion. TAC will need to see how this can best be achieved,

It is obvious that the first workshops on a specific topic is meant to understand different approaches and views. For each topic relevant for FDOs follow-up working meetings, working groups or taskforces need to be planned. Every interested expert is invited to participate, i.e., the plans will be made open.

Globally Integrated Dataspace

We wanted to initiate a discussion about the name of the evolving global domain of digital artefacts which should be as easy to understand as names such as Internet, Web, FAIR, etc. Yet, we realised that it was too early. Many are now using a popular term **Globally Integrated Dataspace** which is makes use of the term “dataspace” each of which points to a set of technologies and rules chosen. In several meetings also with industry we illustrated that FDOs are excellent units to travel between these many different dataspace currently being built. This is due to the fact that FDOs are autonomous, self-supporting units of FAIR information that exist independent of the choices for specific technologies and rule sets.

Institutional Support

The Leiden Declaration prepared for the conference in Leiden was signed by ?? experts which gave an excellent message. But it was also noted that there was some critique about the process and formulations.

The FDOF will now turn back to the question of institutional support which we postponed due to the Leiden conference. We will soon start a campaign for an institutional support of the FDOF work. No money and obligations are being asked.

FDOF - Industry Interaction

Our interactions with industry continued fostered mainly by the bridging role of the DIN standardisation organisation. Together with Gaia-X, the FDOF was invited again to contribute to the DIN FOCUS ICT Meeting on “dataspaces”. We also invited experts working in industry related projects such as Industry 4.0 Asset Administration Shell and International Dataspace Association to contribute to our workshops and will have a lecture on Gaia-X Federation Services at 29.6. We will continue these interactions since we are convinced that the FDOF needs to participate in bridge building.

Responsible for this FDO Bulletin are the FDO-SC Co-Chairs:
Christine Kirkpatrick, Dimitris Koureas, George Strawn, Peter Wittenburg
Comments/question can be sent to secretariat@fairdo.org

